

MY MEDIA EDUCATION EDUCATION IN THE PROCESS EDUCATION OF RECIPIENTS PERSONAL IN THE PROJECT PLACE

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Abstract : This theses education in the system media education its importance education of recipients personal to occur adding contribution and education to the process about modern technology through students about get about about action analysis do Media education modern education in the process national education receivers for comfortable and efficient study environment should , maybe report creativity , communicative to the eye and independent thinking identity is also important in development tool about In the article about , number literacy , virtual platforms , social media and interactive teaching students personal at work also seeing the place will be released .

Key words : media education , education private , private content , number literacy , creativity , communicative to the eye , independent thinking , virtual platforms , interactive education , social media

Introduction : Education to the process media education current received modern education in the system revolutionary changes is making Media education national students knowledge with provide , perhaps report personal to occur Ham big effect it's great . Education in the process modern technologies apply through students knowledge get process more active and interactive being

Media education personality

Media education this education process number and interactive technology by is enrichment . This is the method information for through of students education get process more interesting and efficient to do by .

Media education is it information and contact technologies (ICT) production education in the process apply through knowledge get , knowledge to give and knowledge exchange process interaction , innovation and efficient about in terms of holder is an organization . Media education to students education in the process different different media other , personal , digital platforms , internet, video, graphics , virtual environments and social companies through information get and mutually communication to do by .

My media education about purpose education traditional of methods away , modern technology with is enrichment . In Bujarayan students independent to learn , creative to thinking , critical to the analysis and fast information get to the eye have will be , my media education to students knowledge takes own

personal rights and to issues suitable ravish adaptation Companies are also individuals .

Media education of students number literacy attitude , communicative the eye development and their modern society looking suitable so to prepare help .

Digital literacy and his place

Digital literacy is number technology , internet and different electron device by to information access , of them Go , the information need , exchange , analysis to do and about is watching . today in the day number literacy modern in society Great activity conduct for necessary a lie about from his eyes is one .

Media education through personalized teaching event :

1. **Students for suitable at speed learning about :** Media education technologies to the students education process to themselves comfortable at speed take to go by . Each one student topics himself for comfortable in time , own personal to issues suitable ravish to learn can For example , video lessons Again view , materials own about study or different from the tests repeated transition by there is .

2. **Online courses and to resources login :** Media education through present done online courses and education each of the platforms to the student own help suitable courses about questions . These are resources of students knowledge takes independent and about so union signs one Each student own to issues suitable clear individual education program things can

3. **His own to do and himself control do :** Media education to the students own knowledge about to do and himself control to do by event Online tests , interactive about and in real time mastery shows time students more active to study encourages . Personal to do another through students which in topics knowledge about big knowing they get

4. **Adapted education programs :** Media education each of the technologies individual to the student customized education programs present reach questions Example for , artificial intelligence by help education platforms of the student before knowledge and rights based on new lessons adapting . This while education the place then

5. **Interactive study Materials :** Media education for to the students interactive lesson materials present does Ush materials (video, infographics , games , virtual laboratories) students attraction to do and lessons interesting to do through appropriation process at the individual level created Each student to himself suitable so education get for interactive of products through can

6. **Remote education about** : Media education to students before from the place and before in time education get questions .Remote education process of students personal by and vital plans suitable ravish education that they get one This is especially true work schedule or personal enterprises with One in time education takes for students for it is convenient .

7. **Permanent Again contact and help** : Media education to the students fast Again contact get questions event Online platforms and virtual owners through students own to the questions answer take or necessary support to find can It's up to them study in the process themselves to feel free and independent ravish knowledge to get help .

8. **Motivation and to himself has been confidence by** : Personalized education process through students own achievements sure seeing they go , that's it while report motivation then Personal to goals possible and independent thing rustle to students to themselves has been confidence in life help .

Summary : Media education through personalized education of students about and rights in consideration received beam education process interactive and customized so union about possibility . These are buildings to students to themselves suitable at speed , private help about knowledge get and education the place about questions .

Media education personalized education development by . Students own by and help suitable education to get can And this report to education a lie work after and personal to occur development effect do

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